

Kilvey Hill and Woodlands

**Kilvey Hill
Woodland Volunteers**

Ecological Constraints and Opportunities Plan (ECOP)

Version 3 (January 2023)

Introduction	3
Background	4
Regeneration begins	5
Forestry compartments	7
Tree diseases	9
Fire damage	10
Skyline: the proposed lease extent	11
Soil and vegetation types	13
Habitat Fragmentation: Risks and Issues	14
General issues for Kilvey Woodlands	17
Opportunities for mitigation and compensation	18

Left: The Kilvey Arch erected in March 2001. Carved out of a single trunk of oak by artist Nansi Hemming. The panels chronicle life and nature on the Hill from prehistoric times to the present day.

This edition is January 2023. This is the third version based on information received from a meeting with Swansea Council at the Environment Centre on Friday 9 December 2022 and consultations and discussions with Kilvey Hill volunteers and woodland users.

Text and research by Nigel Robins (nrcontact30@gmail.com)

ECOP: Issue Map	18
Risks and issues	19
The Stepwise Approach and Kilvey Woodland	20
References and Further Reading	21

This Ecological constraints and opportunities plan (ECOP) is based on the suggested content of an ECOP as described in BS 42020:2013 p17-18. Information is added as it becomes publicly available to the Kilvey Woodland Volunteers.

This ECOP may cover issues arising from the proposed redevelopment of a large tract of Kilvey Woodlands by Skyline Enterprises, a foreign tourism company.

The general contents of an ECOP are described as:

- a) Areas and features on and off site, including appropriate buffer areas that, by virtue of their importance, are to be retained and avoided by both development activities and the overall footprint of development (see Annex G for potentially harmful activities).*
- b) Areas and features where opportunities exist to undertake mitigation and compensation.*
- c) Areas and features with potential for biodiversity enhancement.*
- d) Areas and features that will be affected adversely by the proposed development, e.g. through loss or reduction of habitat and/or severance or disturbance of critical habitat linkages.*
- e) Areas where ongoing biodiversity conservation management is required to prevent deterioration in condition during construction/implementation.*
- f) Areas needing protection on site and/or in adjacent areas (e.g. from physical damage on site or pollution downstream) during the construction process.*
- g) Areas where biosecurity measures are necessary to manage the risk of spreading pathogens or non-native invasive species.*

INTRODUCTION

Kilvey Hill is an iconic part of Swansea and the significance of the Hill to Swansea residents and visitors will increase in the future as it increasingly becomes a highly visible green space adjoining the urban centre of the city.

The woodland is a superb example of post-industrial recovery of a heavily polluted landscape and better communication of its past and its future significance should be made at every opportunity.

Although the land was never officially part of the Lower Swansea Valley (LSV) Project, the recreated woodland is already part of the historic achievements of Swansea Corporation, the University and the other agencies that collaborated on the recovery. The species planted in the 1970s were based on the knowledge gained by the remarkable botanical and chemical work of the LSV Project. This means that the woodland itself is an historic part of the recovery of Swansea from the consequences of two hundred years of pollution and dereliction from the great industrial concerns that transformed the Lower Swansea Valley. The predominance of Lodgepole, Corsican and Scots pines across the woodland is because of the resilience of those trees in the toxic soils of the Hill. Many of those 'pioneer' trees are now sick or old and their work has been done. The large amount of natural native tree regeneration in the clearings and gaps on the Hill demonstrates that the healing and recovery process for woodland is well underway. The conversion or transition from coniferous woodland to broadleaf has already begun and the natural processes of regeneration should be supported wherever possible.

The increasing momentum of natural regeneration should make the need for any formal planting schemes unnecessary.

Some of the original pines that were planted in the 1970s have grown to impressive size and are still safe and healthy. They should be considered as historic artifacts and assets because they were part of that original pioneering effort to tackle the pollution left by previous generations. This kind of 'post-industrial woodland' is a significant part of the landscape recovery and rejuvenation of the industrial parts of Wales. Post-industrial woodland takes its place alongside Ancient Woodland, Ancient Semi-natural Woodland and Plantations on Ancient Woodland as important assets of landscape recovery and adaptation to new climatic conditions.

As the woodland has grown, so has its use and connections with the local communities that surround Kilvey. A thriving volunteer organisation has provided thousands of hours of voluntary time to care and protect the land and is one of many organisations and groups that use the woodlands for wellbeing and recreational activities.

Left: By the 1790s, Kilvey Hill was severely affected by the toxic copper smoke from the White Rock and Hafod smelting works. This was also the time of the destruction of the last of Swansea's riverside meadows as they were covered with toxic copper slag which would also be freely dumped onto Kilvey in the nineteenth century.

Below: Kilvey Hill was heavily mined for coal from early medieval times. In the 1830s, the Hill was an important centre of geological study as famous pioneer geologists William Logan and Henry De La Beche used the coal mines on Kilvey to map all of Swansea's coal seams. This is part of the original geology map of Swansea from 1845. The concentration of coal seams can be seen opposite White Rock Copper Works.

Background

The woodlands of Kilvey Hill are barely forty years old. They came from nothing, or more correctly, they were created out of the heavily polluted wastelands created by the White Rock copper works and the other primary Lower Swansea Valley polluters. The Hill dominates Swansea, and most residents know of it. It forms the backdrop to the city. It's practically crying out for a big 'Hollywood' style sign in the style of the Los Angeles original. However, people would disagree on using the original Viking name (corrupted to Swansea) or the Welsh name (Abertawe). A combination of both would take up much space. The Hill is intimately related to the history of Swansea. However, as it's on the east side of the River Tawe, its inclusion in the administrative boundaries is as recent as the nineteenth century (Griffiths 1990: 53). Today, the Hill is primarily green and covered with various trees. The urban curse of frequent fires punctuates dry months, sadly typical for much Welsh woodland. For Swansea natives, Kilvey Hill dominates the city's central space, albeit alongside its more urbanised western neighbour of Townhill.

Kilvey has reflected centuries of Swansea life. It undoubtedly started as a heavily wooded coastal hill. The woods were gradually removed after 1100 providing building materials and resources for the town. The bigger trees of the primary woodland may have disappeared by the time the Normans arrived in the 1100s. The secondary woodland would have gone through successive cycles of growth and destruction in response to the fortunes of early Swansea (Kowarik 2005: 4–7). An early appreciation of the Kilvey coal deposits meant that the hill is honeycombed with over 700 years of coal workings. The prevailing westerly winds ensured that Kilvey endured most of the pollution of Swansea's industrial revolution destroying the ecosystem and ruining the land. Since 1970, the Kilvey environmental story has gradually recovered to what we see today.

The restoration and repair of the ecosystem of Kilvey, whilst not perfect, is a remarkable story of environmental planning and care and is one of the enduring benefits of the adjoining Lower Swansea Valley Project of the 1960s, which did so much to repair the valley and remediate the dreadful pollution from the metal industries that scarred both land and people (Hilton 1967).

Above: The chronic pollution on Kilvey Hill remains under a thin layer of newly generated soil in the regenerating woodlands. Any excavations will exposed the layer as seen here.

Right: In 1970 the Forestry Commission leased a large portion of the land that became Kilvey woodland and used several methods to reseed and fertilise the surface to allow regeneration to occur.

Regeneration begins

The chaotic style of industrial growth in nineteenth-century Swansea had, by the 1960s, left a legacy of complex and complicated leasehold and freehold land ownership in the valley and on Kilvey. Land on Kilvey had been acquired by the various operators of White Rock from the early 1800s for tipping of waste and to avoid compensation to farmers and landowners for the poisoned land. In the 1960s and 1970s, the Swansea Council estate agents, often the unsung heroes of land restoration and repair of land, worked hard to bring the chaos into ordered public ownership (Bromley and Humphrys 1979: 11). Dealing with the land assembly and ownership of the industrial valley was a complex task, but Kilvey proved equally challenging. By 1969, the whole Lower Swansea Valley Project area, including Kilvey adjoining, had been recognised, categorised, and labelled. Of the 70 'plots' identified, the 'mountain' of Kilvey became known as Plot 57 (Bromley and Humphrys 1979: 186–89). Brutally bureaucratic possibly, but Kilvey, for the first time in decades, had an identity beyond the ignominy of being the 'White Rock Tip'.

The newly designated Plot 57 now had an identity and a spatial extent and work could begin to address the devastation. By late 1969 Plot 57 was jointly managed by Swansea Council and the Forestry Commission (Bromley and Humphrys 1979:

187). Restoration could begin.

Plot 57 now had the benefit of consideration and thought into how it could be valued environmentally for the first time in centuries. The relationship between the land and the town could be re-evaluated, and remediation, restoration, ecosystems and recreation could now be considered. The role of the central valley (Nant Llywnheiernin) was probably last considered important in the early 1800s as a source of industrial waterpower. Still, now it had a new significance in ecology, amenity and nature. Removing tip waste and restoring the central valley of the Nant Llywnheiernin was a priority. Centuries of coal mining had irretrievably diminished the surging water of the original stream. However, the upper portion of the valley still suggests the impressive size of the original stream from the 1600s. Removal of tip material throughout 1969 revealed the true extent of the damage with destroyed soil, lifeless debris, craters, and scars left by bulldozers. The heavy equipment proved to be a benefit in moving the massive lumps of slag and even the substantial glacial boulders that littered the hill. By the end of 1969, the Council had created a remarkably faithful reinstatement of the original stream valley (Borough Engineer, Surveyor and Planning Officer's Department 1969: 3–4).

The present-day Kilvey Woodland is a complex mix of Forestry Commission commercial species trees planned for timber production and a series of open mosaic habitats created where fires, tree disease and windthrow have created space for natural regeneration. Regeneration of the natural vegetation has accelerated in the past twenty years. Natural regeneration is more fire resilient than the original plantation trees and is gradually taking over the ordered planting of the original woodland. Kilvey is rapidly generating a locally appropriate natural association of resilient vegetation led by significant oak regrowth.

Forestry Compartments

When the forestry Commission leased a portion of the Hill in 1970 it followed best practice by planning a series of compartments for management and maintenance. The northern compartments were laid out in 1970 and the southern extent was created later in the 1980s.

We have archival compartment information from the early plantings. The Commission were understandably nervous in being asked to establish commercial forestry in a distinctly urban area. There was also a challenge in choosing commercial tree species that would flourish in the heavily polluted areas of the Hill. The most polluted area of the Hill was retained under the management of Swansea Council.

Compartmental planting took place between 1970 and approximately 1987. This helped ensure some variation in the ages of the various stands on the Hill.

The snapshots on the following page explain how the woodland was originally structured. Alongside the Forestry Commission, Swansea Council also planted some significant trees on their piece of retained land which forms the western side of the woodland where the Kilvey Woodland Volunteers Glade activity area is situated.

As the current Skyline proposals only affect the northern woodland, the snapshots on the following page concentrate on that area.

1. The current compartment layout that we know of.

4. 1980 saw addition of more Lodgepole pine in the north over what was originally very polluted slag waste. By this time the concept of urban amenity woodland was emerging.

A series of snapshots of what we know of the planting history of the woodland. Although less apparent today, the compartments do reflect a multi-age plantation structure. That multi-age planting which gives us the profile we see today. Perhaps most culturally significant are images 7 and 8 which are the first trees planted on the western hill since the early 1700s, and show the pioneering spirit and leadership of the Swansea Council planning and parks departments in the early 1970s. Image 7 shows the locations of the pioneering Scots Pines raised in the Morriston Gasworks Nursery as part of the Lower Swansea Valley Project of the 1960s. Image 8 shows the enclosure of Monterey Pines planted in 1970 and which are now the largest trees on the hill.

2. The compartments originally planted in 1970 with Lodgepole pine, Scots pine, and hybrid larch.

5. 1987 saw more infills of mixed conifers.

7. In late 1969 in advance of the lease to the Forestry Commission, Swansea Council planted a series of Scots pines as an experiment in 'amenity planting'. Many of these first trees on the Hill still survive.

3. 1977 saw additional planting of Lodgepole pine and Corsican pine.

6. 1987-1990 saw more infills of mixed conifers, which completed the forest planting of the area.

8. In 1970 Swansea Council also planted a stand of Monterey pines. Montereys have a strong affinity with South Wales coal tip planting. Many of these trees have flourished and are the largest trees on the Hill.

Tree diseases

Unsurprisingly, the Kilvey Woodland has been severely affected by the tree diseases that are common in coniferous plantations. This is also a reflection of the lack of good forestry practice on the hill by Forestry Commission Wales and NRW in the last twenty years. The weak health of many of the trees as they struggle on the polluted land has made them susceptible to infections and weak rootplates lead to considerable windthrow in the more exposed southern area.

Clearfelling and replanting with native species could be targeted in these areas or at least prioritised in management plans.

Above left: Areas of significant tree disease in the coniferous forest in the summer of 2022. This is likely to be an under recording of problems. The plantations are also under stress because of drought conditions, arson attacks, lack of thinning and poor root plate establishment on the thin soils.

Above: Areas of clearance quickly attract natural regeneration although, the lack of woodland plant seed store in the ground means it is unlikely we would see rapid natural woodland regeneration although oak seedlings have been prominent in the last five years.

Above: Unfortunately, deliberate arson attacks in the woodlands are a regular occurrence. Arson in urban woodlands was a major concern of the Forestry Commission in the early 1970s and remains a problem. In this instance firefighters had been placed around one of the notable Monterey pines in the summer of 2022. The Monterey is noted for its natural resilience to wildfire in its native regions and is seen as a very apt choice for Welsh urban coastal woodlands.

Above right: Areas of fire devastation in 2022. This wider map takes in the areas of the proposed Skyline leasehold to illustrate that much of the Skyline leasehold will require significant replanting investment (with a consequent risk of fire and loss) to make the area visibly attractive from the town centre.

Fire damage

Kilvey Hill has been blighted by wildfire and arson attacks since the woodlands were planted in the 1970s. Arson attacks outweigh instances of wildfire, although climate change and increasing summer temperatures have resulted in increasing risk of wildfire outbreaks. . The dead and decaying coniferous plantation is a good source of fuel and burns easily. Locally appropriate natural vegetation is more resilient to fire attacks and regenerate very quickly after a fire attack. The plan above is based on field survey in the summer of 2022, it is likely to be an under recording of damaged areas.

Any new or replanted woodland will need to be planned and designed with

fire protection and resilience in mind following latest best practice in woodland design.

We would expect a comprehensive Fire Risk Analysis of all woodlands (old, new and proposed) as part of the due diligence of any development. A significant part of the most vulnerable fire risk areas of the woodlands will fall within the extent of the proposed leasehold extent of the Skyline development as shown on the following pages.

Skyline Enterprises: the proposed lease extent

The proposed leasehold extent to Skyline Enterprises that we have seen will cover approximately 36 hectares of the Kilvey Woodlands, adding greatly to a risk of habitat fragmentation of the recovering woodland. The land is edged red on this

plan. There is a combination of public and private land and a surrender of the Good Leasehold land (the green land here) once held by Natural Resources Wales (NRW) has already occurred. At the time of writing this report, the land assembly for additional additions of adverse possession land was still being completed. The land sought to be acquired by the Council under Possessory Title will be of crucial

importance to the scheme because it appears to include the main base of restaurant buildings and services associated with the Skyline proposal close to the summit of Kilvey Hill.

The land proposed as being leased to Skyline Enterprises includes a significant part of the most challenging land on the Hill. The plan on this page shows the Skyline leasehold in relation to fire damage and tree disease.

We expect there to be considerable investment in woodland repair and improvement for the leased land. This will be important for Skyline in creating an attractive venue for their operations and, more importantly, a significant woodland asset for the community once Skyline leave. This will be fair as the Skyline concrete luge runs will permanently blight a large area of land in the north-east of the leasehold extent.

The leasehold extent misses the notable Scots Pines and Monterey Pines areas although we expect these to be protected and enhanced by Swansea Council's woodland strategy for the area as there will need to be considerable investment in the fire and disease-damaged areas shown here lying to the north of the leasehold land.

There is also confusion and uncertainty over footpaths and cycle tracks.

The luge runs and operational buildings of Skyline will disrupt some of the most important footpaths and tracks that link the communities of Port Tennant and St Thomas to the woodland areas of the Hill. We can expect some reworking of paths to allow for easier hill access and a 'rewiring' of the paths network in and around the Skyline development.

The same is true for the cycle tracks which concentrate on a small part of the leasehold as shown on the inset map here.

Above: The Skyline leasehold extent will contain a large proportion of the woodland that has disease and fire damage. We can expect considerable investment in woodland repair and restoration should the development progress.

Left: Cycle tracks concentrate in a small area of the Skyline leasehold extent. This may be complicated by the subsequent use of some of these tracks as ad hoc walking trails. Despite considerable investment in the past, not all of the once high-quality cycle trails are used regularly. Some have been given over to motor bike riders.

Above: The species variation of the original plantation was restricted to commercial trees and thus had no diversity. This is typical for Forestry Commission planting in earlier days. However, Welsh Government policies have changed considerably in past years and modern planting will undoubtedly have far more species diversity to support modern principles of biodiversity and well being and restoration of degraded land. Below is a typical modern planting scheme considered bird-friendly and supportive of modern restoration techniques.

Replanting needs to be carefully planned and monitored and support trees and plants of local provenance and locally appropriate resilient species. Ironically, the hardest tree species in the Kilvey woodland is the non-native Monterey Pine. This species has earned its place on the hill because of its resilience to fire drought and poisoned land.

We expect to have a comprehensive planting scheme for regeneration which is open to scrutiny and agreement for practicality and suitability.

Soil and vegetation types

In the 1960s, the surface of Kilvey hill was extremely challenging for the establishment of any forestry. After two centuries of toxic air pollution from the industries of the Lower Swansea Valley, the natural vegetation had been killed or diminished and the soil severely degraded. Kilvey's soil is an upland brown earth derived from the underlying Pennant Sandstone rock. There are some pockets of sandy clay and erratic rocks of glacial origin. The lower slopes are contaminated with waste and copper smelting slags albeit landscaped into natural appearance by the landscaping of the late 1960s.

The Hill is in an exposed situation facing Swansea Bay with a high gale incidence. The windthrow on the southern side of the current woodland is extensive and dangerous.

The poor soil on the slopes resulted in vegetation of heather and bilberry in a form of open mosaic habitat although it was never fully formed and always prone to erosion and destruction by fire. Some impeded drainage in the centre of the proposed Skyline lease area is dominated by purple moor grass and some rhododendron.

The typical response of the Forestry Commission was to plant pines, mainly Scots, Lodgepole and Corsican. Larch (Japanese and Hybrid) was also added in the compartmentation and planting phases as described on pages 7-8.

A large part of the hill was ploughed in advance of planting, although some areas were clearly not ploughed as shown by the survival of a range of eighteenth-century leats constructed to improve water supply to the White Rock copper works. These leats retain moisture even in the driest months and may be regarded as biodiversity hotspots within the plantation woodlands.

The original tree planting was limited in species variation, as the Forestry Commission was still pre-determined to plant commercial species. Subsequent growth of trees in all stands proved disappointing because of the poor and toxic soils and it is unlikely that a commercial return could ever have been obtained. The coniferous forest provided a substantial service in covering the bare valley hillsides and still contribute significantly to the green appearance of Kilvey Hill today. Changes in management processes and land appraisal in the 1990s saw the land being perceived as being community woodland rather than commercial plantation. This view of the Hill was maintained by Natural Resources Wales (the forestry Commission's successor organisation in Wales) up until the surrender of their lease of the woodland and the return of the land to the landlord (Swansea Council) in mid-2022. At a meeting with council staff on 9 December 2022, the council informed the Kilvey Woodland Volunteer Group of their intention to create a Woodland Management Plan for the area.

Fire damage and tree disease (as described on pages 9-11) has meant that a significant area (over fifteen hectares) may be severely damaged. The ruderal vegetation that has appeared in these areas may take many years to transform into woodland.

Prior to the surrender of their lease, NRW were in the process of preparing a new management plan for the hill including a management strategy to transition woodland from coniferous plantation to native woodland. There is an

assumption that these original plans are now discarded and Swansea Council will create new plans, although these will still have to conform to the wider strategies of the Welsh Government's *Woodlands for Wales Strategy* and the *UK Woodland Assurance Standard*. Equally, the NRW Good Practice Guide on Forest Resilience and structural diversity in Welsh woodlands has a great deal of important advice.

Locally, in recent years, two new woodlands have been established on post-industrial wasteland or challenging land by the Woodland Trust/Coed Cadw. These new woodlands at Ffos Las and Brynau have been created from open land to the highest modern standards and could act as useful reference sites for new woodland management on Kilvey. The Ffos las Woodland has particular relevance because it was founded predominantly on open cast spoil tips.

Above: Recent Lidar imagery of the Kilvey woodlands reveals the remarkable survival of many of the eighteenth-century leats constructed to harvest waterpower for the White Rock Copper Works. Some of the leats are repurposed to provide bike tracks and walking paths. Others survive in an original state. The water geography of the hill has been irreparably destroyed by past coal mining and many streams and leats are dry most of the year. However these leats frequently retain moisture and provide shelter for plants and animals throughout the conifer plantations and are biodiversity hotspots.

Habitat Fragmentation: Risks and Issues

The proposed extent of the Skyline leasehold raises risks of habitat fragmentation and loss of ecosystem services and functions. Currently, it is hard to accept Council insistence that land will not be fenced or excluded because the luge runs and service areas will need to be fenced or barriers erected to provide security and public safety. Kilvey is notorious for challenging behaviours and remains a focus for stolen cars and arson. Improving access to the hill presents more risk of these behaviours occurring involving disruption to local residents and increased emergency services and policing costs.

Equally, the estimated extent of concrete luge runways promises considerable disruption to the land and may provide dangerous barriers to wildlife movements and walkers. We currently can't see an arrangement where the luge run area is open to access.

The precise boundaries of the Skyline lease neatly bisect the full extent of the recovering woodland on the hill. Whilst we obviously could not expect the entire extent of Skyline land to be fenced, even if that was possible, we currently believe that there will have to be significant barriers and/or security for key aspects of the infrastructure. We are surprised that Swansea Council believes this will not be the case, however we may not have the detailed information on the scheme that the council already has.

Although precise national understanding of habitat connectivity is still at an early stage, we know enough via research from RSPB, NRW, and English Nature/

Above: Burnt car debris in the centre of the Skyline leasehold extent in December 2022. Open access to the Skyline leasehold area with improved roads will need better security and control.

Natural England to make accurate broad assumptions about impact and threat when developments such as this are proposed.

At this point it is worth repeating the Lawton Principles from the ground-breaking 'Making space for Nature Report, not least because they were universally accepted as profound common sense across all sectors of agriculture, government and conservation when they emerged.

They are:

- Improve the quality of existing sites by better habitat management and reduced Pressures
- Increase the size of existing wildlife sites
- Enhance connections between sites, either through physical corridors or 'stepping stones'
- Create new sites
- Reduce the pressures on wildlife by improving the wider environment, including through buffering wildlife sites

These principles are short enough for most people amateur or expert, inside or

Above; Although hampered by a lack of publicly available data, the plans we have seen suggest the concrete luge runs will impact approximately fifteen hectares of land as shown here. It remains hard to accept this land will be open to access as it will be dangerous to mix cyclists, walkers and luge users. Equally, lighting the concrete race tracks may affect wildlife. The width of the tracks, which is estimated to be on average 4.5m may have Sustainable Urban Drainage (SUDS) issues, particularly in climate-change related heavy rainfall events .

Currently we must assume this land will be securely contained , which means fencing. This estimate of fifteen hectares is based on latest available public data and is likely to be an under estimate.

We could not see any constraints to the luge run planning on the available data to take into account the antenna compound or significant archaeology around the summit of Kilvey Hill. Therefore we know this plan is subject to significant change.

outside the planning system, or political or non-political to agree and support. They were planned that way.

We can take these principles further in a non-controversial way by agreeing that there are five things needed for an ecological network to be effective:

1. Core areas – these are the areas of highest wildlife value.
2. Corridors and stepping stones – the places that allow movement and interaction Restoration areas – areas where species and habitats can be restored.
3. Buffer zones – these protect the core areas, corridors, stepping stones and restoration areas from the pressures of human influence.
4. Sustainable use areas – areas of greater human influence and resource use.

Above: The basic Lawton Principles in action. Kilvey is a combination of restoration areas, developing core areas, corridors and buffer zones. Swansea Council and its new leasehold tenant (Skyline) can now deliver greatly improved restoration and repair of the woodlands.

It is useful to understand that before 1970, none of the land we are discussing could be considered part of the natural environment. The destruction of the hill and the Tawe valley to the west was total. Everything we see and enjoy today has grown up since the mid-1970s. The redevelopment and recovery was at the expense of the public purse. There was negligible (if any) private sector input into the regeneration, they disappeared once the profits declined. What we see today was hard won with public money, partnerships with the local University, government agencies and local communities. The ethos of community giving and volunteering is maintained by the Kilvey Woodland Volunteers in a direct line back to the pioneering work of Stephen Lavender and local schoolchildren who planted so many trees in in the 1960s.

So, hopefully everyone concerned about the hill (including Swansea Council) should be able to agree that the habitat we have today was hard won over many years. Regardless of the current (arguable) conservation status of the land, it is local land regenerated with enormous cost in terms of public money and volunteer hours. That investment over decades has got us to where we are today and needs to be taken into account when we weigh up the benefits and disbenefits of chopping a lot of it down and losing it under concrete and behind fencing of a foreign investment company.

Habitat loss is different from habitat fragmentation. We experienced loss when the copper industries destroyed the ecology of Kilvey and the east side in the past three centuries. Habitat fragmentation is no less pernicious although harder to identify and quantify. The Skyline development plans will undoubtedly create either loss or fragmentation

Below: University staff show new tree seedlings to schoolchildren in the Morriston 'Gasworks' Nursery in the late 1960s. The nursery provided hundreds of young trees for valley research plantations, probably including the Scots and Monterey Pines described on page 8.

or perhaps both. The calculation of loss or fragmentation will be complicated by the differing perceptions of biodiversity under coniferous woodland with further complications of the impacts of tree disease and fire damage. Initial conversations with Council representatives left us with an impression that the land will be characterised as a 'blob' of problem land with little of worth evident. We still await the series of ecological surveys claimed to have been conducted by Skyline over the past few years but as these were seemingly conducted in secret, we currently have little confidence in their veracity or quality. We know there is significant presence of reptiles, bats, mammals and birds across the hill although quantitative surveys are lacking. We know that records from the National Biodiversity Network (NBN) and the South East Wales Biodiversity Records Centre (SEWBREC) are poor but as always in ecology, absence of evidence does not mean evidence of absence.

Because the leasehold extent appears to bisect the woodland, there will inevitably be a concern over fragmentation and loss of connectivity north and south of the Skyline development. This will need careful and sensitive management and we expect to see how this is addressed. We did expect to see this and other issues already raised by the Council's Planning Ecologist as part of a Preliminary Ecological Assessment (PEA), but despite requests we are still waiting to be told who the Planning Ecologist for the proposed project is and how much preliminary work has been done. This is rather confusing as we have been told that Skyline have already completed some ecological assessments but we don't understand how this could have happened without involvement of the Planning Ecologist. This is all clearly described in Swansea Council's own Supplementary Planning Guidance which the Council Leader Rob Stewart confirmed would be followed in the liaison meeting of 9 December 2022.

The important issues arising from habitat fragmentation are known and have been described clearly in many documents and guidance. Some of these may affect Kilvey Woodland in either its Skyline development land or the redevelopment of the coniferous woodland into a native forest. Key issues for discussion could be:

- Subdivision of species' habitat into smaller patches, some of which might be too small to continue to support populations of a species, or to maintain stable / viable populations (or metapopulations across multiple sites) in the long term. (Low to Medium Risk).
- Isolation of habitat patches and reduction of successful species immigration and emigration. This can increase the likelihood of inbreeding and loss of genetic diversity, and of local population extinction through chance events (combined with a decline in the likelihood of re-colonisation). This could become an increasingly serious issue as the climate continues to change and populations in isolated patches are both at higher risk of being affected by extreme events and unable to shift as their suitable climatic environment 'moves'. (Medium Risk).
- Edge effects' – environmental changes that occur at the boundary between one type of land cover and another (for example disturbance from a human-modified area affecting an adjacent patch of semi-natural vegetation). These can include both biotic and abiotic effects, such as structural damage or change to vegetation; changed temperature, light

and evaporation levels; altered nutrient cycling; the deposition of fertilisers and pesticides; changed patterns of plant growth, and increased effects of predators and invasive species. Some of these effects can penetrate a long way into a patch. (High Risk).

- Impaired function of some ecosystem processes, such as hydrological flows. This can affect the stability and viability of the system and not only its capacity to provide habitat for species (as outlined above) but also the services it provides to people. The hydrology of the hill has been dramatically changed by coal mining over the past two hundred years. (High Risk).

Above: The relationship between Kilvey Woodlands and nearby Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI) edged red on the above image. The large extent of Crymlyn Bog lies 1.2km east of the hill. The smaller Six Pit, Swansea Vale and White Rock SSSI is in two parts, the smaller portion in White Rock is 325m west of the woodlands, and the larger portion is 893m north of the northern boundary of the woodlands. It is too much to claim connectivity with these sites but it does illustrate the value of the Kilvey Woodlands in providing significant habitat space between them. The whole of the woodland falls within the Site of Interest for Nature Conservation (SINC) shown in blue. The SINC is an extremely large area and we expect there to be clear strategies for the provision of opportunities for priority species and habitat creation in accordance with Policy ER 6 of the Local Development Plan.

Above: The Kilvey Woodlands can be considered as 'connected' to the young developing woodlands of the river corridor lying to the west. However all the woodlands are very young and no trees are older than about twenty years with the oldest being conifers. There is currently very little opportunity for trees to develop 'veteran' features such as scars or holes that provide additional habitat opportunities. These will occur in due course, providing the woodlands are left alone long enough to naturally develop such features. Equally, tree veteranisation will not help as the trees are too small to be modified. Caution must be used in considering the installation of nest boxes as in the valley and on the hill as they are often the focus of vandalism and violence against animals. Although declining, the use of firearms and weapons is still common. The woods are bordered on the

southern side by what was originally seen as heathland, now heavily damaged by fire. We would expect there to be a rigorous repair and restoration plan for the border between the woodlands and fire-damaged heathlands. A major challenge for connectivity is the presence of the A4217 road along the western border of Kilvey. This wide and fast road is a constant threat to birds and other wildlife and road mortality of wildlife will most likely increase as the woodland matures. Of particular risk are young owls which are susceptible to collisions with fast moving traffic. Urban and industrial areas are hatched black.

General Issues for Kilvey Woodlands

Area of most significant environmental features

Plans for disposal of wastes, removal of site buildings and final site clearances.

Kilvey Woodland based on the original NRW Leasehold Extent Summer 2022.

Enterprise Park Woodland compartment. Young, mixed woodland habitat.

Area of most significant burn and tree disease damage.

Plan needed for removal and cutting of trees and ground vegetation, including a time plan and seasonal constraints.

All ecological surveys should follow good practice guidelines in accordance with CIEEM Technical Guidance Series Guidance for Preliminary Ecological appraisals.

Foxhole Open Mosaic Habitat (tinted yellow)

Clarity on site setup plans including site huts, storage areas, latrines and drainage. Site lighting, Petroleum, Oil, Lubricant storage, and haul road plans

Plan for installation of underground services and any watercourse diversion, water abstraction or discharges

The main portion of the leasehold extent to be demised to Skyline enterprises

Area of concrete luge runs affecting the land surface

Plans for workflows including night-time working, dust and noise and increased traffic movements.

Details of piling or foundation work for all structures and any clash with archaeological features.

Arrangements for dealing with vandalism, fires and burning of wastes, pollution incidents, fuel leaks and spills.

Opportunities for mitigation and compensation

Plans for better habitat connectivity with the riverside woodland corridor.

Improve woodland edge transitions on existing paths and compartment boundaries.

Improve transition from open mosaic habitat into woodland

Remove diseased conifers in selected compartments and replace with locally appropriate

Replace tracks and paths destroyed by the Skyline developments and improve standards and accessibility.

Create new ponds to improve habitat opportunities. Possibly related to SuDS mitigations.

Largest areas of burn damage.

There is an opportunity to increase the number of ponds and wet woodland features to improve biodiversity

Replace areas of burn damage with new locally appropriate woodland planting.

Redesign new woodland areas with increased resilience to environmental change and wildfire.

Risks and issues

Risk of loss of habitat quality through increase of traffic and higher lighting levels throughout the Skyline operational areas in the construction and operational phases.

Because of building and road developments, there is a risk of disturbance of older coal tips and toxic smelting waste resulting in a dust threat to local residents

Conservation management may be needed in areas of construction traffic and activity.

Approximately 1300m of paths and tracks may have to be replaced or diverted.

Land permanently blighted by concrete runways.

Any fencing may disrupt and even prevent developing wildlife movements .

Risk of severance or disturbance of critical north-south woodland habitat linkage.

Risk of pollution from construction activities affecting water courses.

Risk of loss of open mosaic and woodland habitat in luge runs area.

The Stepwise Approach and Kilvey Woodland

This workflow is derived from Swansea Council's Supplementary Planning Guidance which, we are assured, is to be adhered to throughout the planning and development process

Step A Identify and Assess

Although Swansea Council believe that preliminary ecological assessment has taken place, we have seen no evidence of this and await the confirmation that correct procedures have been followed in accordance with the Supplementary Planning Guidance and BS 42020. We suspect that both SEWBREC and NBN have comparatively few records relating to the Kilvey Woodland. This is a particular concern for protection of amphibians and reptiles in the development areas, and bat activity and roost locations.

We have not yet seen the Swansea Ecological Connectivity assessment for Kilvey Hill.

Step B Avoid

As we are unsure of the precise nature of the apparent preliminary ecological assessment, we are unable to scrutinise plans for avoidance as described in LDP Policies ER 6, 8, and 9.

We are particularly keen to see the assessment of negative impacts of the development. As Kilvey hill is the centre of a particularly large Site of Importance to Nature Conservation (SINC), we expect there to be some interpretation of impacts.

Step C Respond and Design

We await the plans for biodiversity enhancement and green infrastructure for the development.

Step D Mitigate

We await proposals for mitigation that conform to CIEEM guidance.

Steps E to H

To be completed when further information is made available.

References and Further Reading

- 'Biodiversity - Code of Practice for Planning and Development (BS 42020;2013)'. 2013. (British Standards Institution)
- 'Biodiversity and Development: Supplementary Planning Guidance'. 2021. (Swansea Council)
- Bromley, Rosemary D. F., and Graham Humphrys (eds.). 1979. *Dealing With Dereliction: The Redevelopment of the Lower Swansea Valley* (Swansea: University College of Swansea)
- Gilbert, O.L. 1989. *The Ecology of Urban Habitats* (London: Chapman and Hall)
- Government, Welsh. [n.d.]. 'Woodlands for Wales'
- Hanley, Nick, Ken Willis, Neil Powe, and Maggie Anderson. 2002. *Valuing the Benefits of Biodiversity in Forests* (Edinburgh: Forestry Commission)
- Henly, Lauren. 2021. 'Effective Biodiversity Indicators': 7
- Hilton, K. J. (ed.). 1967. *The Lower Swansea Valley Project* (London: Longmans)
- Humphrey, Jonathan, and Sallie Bailey. 2012. *Managing Deadwood in Forests and Woodlands*, Practice Guides (Edinburgh: Forestry Commission)
- Kowarik, Ingo. 2005. 'Wild Urban Woodlands. Towards a Conceptual Framework', in *Wild Urban Woodlands* (Berlin Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag), pp. 1–32
- Parrott, John, and Neil MacKenzie. 2013. *A Critical Review of Work Undertaken to Control Invasive Rhododendron in Scotland* (Edinburgh: Forestry Commission Scotland)
- Rhodes, Mark Alan, William R. Price, and Amy Walker (eds.). 2021. *Geographies of Post-Industrial Place, Memory, and Heritage* (Abingdon: Routledge)
- Robins, Nigel A. 2022. 'The White Rock Works Site, Nant Llwynhiernin and the Kilvey Woodland', *Minerva: The Swansea History Journal*, 30: 54–63

Left: One of the Swansea Council Monterey Pines planted in 1970 on the copper slag debris field. Seen here in the summer of 2022.

